

Supplemental Table 1.
Primary outcomes -
Premenopausal only

	RHI categorical			RHI continuous		
	OR	95% CI	p-value	Coeff	95% CI	p-value
AMH no adjustment	0.99	0.91-1.09	0.90	0.00081	-0.38 to 0.40	0.97
AMH adjusted	1.04	0.93-1.16	0.53	0.025	-0.19 to 0.069	0.26
AMH fully adjusted	1.07	0.94-1.22	0.28	0.050	0.0028 to 0.096	0.04
AFC no adjustment	0.99	0.96-1.03	0.75	-0.0057	-0.020 to 0.0085	0.43
AFC adjusted	1.02	0.97-1.06	0.49	0.0049	-0.012 to 0.022	0.56
AFC fully adjusted	1.03	0.98-1.08	0.18	0.016	-0.0026 to 0.034	0.093

*Adjusted model covariates: age, race, BMI, smoking, income, and education

**Fully adjusted: age, race, BMI, smoking, income, education, hyperlipidemia, hypertension, HOMA-IR, and CRP

Note: RHI values normalized by SD

Supplemental Table 2.
Premenopausal only

	Framingham			Metabolic syndrome		
	Coeff	95% CI	p-value	OR	95% CI	p-value
AMH not adjusted	-0.0022	-0.0035 to -0.00085	<0.001	0.89	0.79-1.00	0.058
AMH adjusted	-0.00045	-0.0057 to -0.00016	0.50	0.92	0.78-1.08	0.32
AMH fully adjusted	-0.00011	-0.0012 to 0.0010	0.85	0.88	0.71-1.09	0.24
AFC not adjusted	-0.00041	-0.00094 to 0.00012	0.13	0.99	0.95-1.03	0.55
AFC adjusted	0.00024	-0.00025 to 0.00072	0.34	1.01	0.96-1.06	0.81
AFC fully adjusted	0.000044	-0.00039 to 0.00047	0.84	0.94	0.87-1.03	0.18

	mtDNA			TL		
	Coeff	95% CI	p-value	Coeff	95% CI	p-value
AMH not adjusted	2.75	-9.15 to 14.65	0.65	0.0095	0.0016 to 0.017	0.02
AMH adjusted	3.33	-10.39 to 17.05	0.63	0.0013	-0.0072 to 0.0097	0.77
AMH fully adjusted	3.29	-11.65 to 18.24	0.44	-0.00057	-0.010 to 0.0089	0.91
AFC not adjusted	1.32	-2.54 to 5.18	0.50	0.0043	0.0014 to 0.0071	0.004
AFC adjusted	1.04	-3.41 to 5.50	0.65	0.0021	-0.0010 to 0.0052	0.19
AFC fully adjusted	2.61	-2.45 to 7.67	0.31	0.0014	-0.0022 to 0.0050	0.45

*Adjusted model covariates: age, race, BMI, smoking, income, and education

**Fully adjusted: age, race, BMI, smoking, income, education, hyperlipidemia, hypertension, HOMA-IR, and CRP

Note: RHI values normalized by SD

Appendix A. Telomere Length Analysis Methods

TL measurement

Peripheral blood mononuclear cells were purified from whole blood collected in Vacutainer® CPT™ Tube with Sodium Citrate (BD, cat # 362761) and cells were stored as dry pellets at -80°C and total genomic DNA was purified using the QIAamp® DNA Mini kit (QIAGEN, Hilden, Germany; Cat. number 51104) in batches. DNA was stored at -80°C for batch telomere length measurement.

Telomere length measurement assay was adapted from Dr. Cawthon's published original method [29-40]. Genomic DNA was extracted from peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) with QIAamp mini DNA extraction kit and quantified by OD260/OD280. The DNA quality control criteria is OD260/OD280 between 1.7-2.0 and concentration greater than 10ng/ μl . All samples in this study passed the DNA quality criteria.

The telomere thermal cycling profile consisted of:

Cycling for T (telomic) PCR: Denature at 96°C for 1 minute; denature at 96°C for 1 second, anneal/extend at 54°C for 60 seconds, with fluorescence data collection, 30 cycles.

Cycling for S (single copy gene) PCR: Denature at 96°C for 1 minute; denature at 95°C for 15 seconds, anneal at 58°C for 1 second, extend at 72°C for 20 seconds, 8 cycles; followed by denature at 96°C for 1 second, anneal at 58°C for 1 second, extend at 72°C for 20 seconds, hold at 83°C for 5 seconds with data collection, 35 cycles.

The primers for the telomere PCR were *tel1b* [5'-CGGTTT(GTTTGG)₅GTT-3'], used at a final concentration of 100 nM, and *tel2b* [5'-GGCTTG(CCTTAC)₅CCT-3'], used at a final concentration of 900 nM. The primers for the single-copy gene (human beta-globin) PCR were *hbg1* [5' GCTTCTGACACAACACTGTGTTCACTAGC-3'], used at a final concentration of 300

nM, and *hbg2* [5'-CACCAACTTCATCCACGTTCCACC-3'], used at a final concentration of 700 nM. The final reaction mix contained 20 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.4; 50 mM KCl; 200 μ M each dNTP; 1% DMSO; 0.4x Syber Green I; 22 ng *E. coli* DNA per reaction; 0.4 Units of Platinum Taq DNA polymerase (Invitrogen Inc.) per 11 microliter reaction; 0.5 - 10 ng of genomic DNA. Tubes containing 26, 8.75, 2.9, 0.97, 0.324 and 0.108ng of a reference DNA (human genomic DNA from buffy coat, Sigma Aldrich cat# 11691112001) were included in each PCR run so that the quantity of targeted templates in each research sample was determined relative to the reference DNA sample by the standard curve method. The same reference DNA was used for all PCR runs. All samples were measured in triplicate wells in 384 well plates and the average of the T and S values were used to calculate the T/S ratios after removal of outliers with the Dixon Q test. The PCR efficiencies were $91.7 \pm 3.9\%$ and $92.1 \pm 6.0\%$ for T reaction and S reaction respectively for this study.

To control for inter-assay variability, 8 control DNA samples were included in each run. In each batch, the T/S ratio of each control DNA was divided by the average T/S for the same DNA from 10 runs to get a normalizing factor. This is done for all 8 samples and the average normalizing factor for all 8 samples was used to correct the participant DNA samples to get the final T/S ratio. The T/S ratio for each sample were measured three times and two closest values were averaged and reported as the final T/S. The assay coefficient variation (CV) is $2.6\% \pm 2.0\%$. Intra-class correlation of repeat DNA extraction (N=48) is $R=0.913$ (95% CI 0.85-0.95).

The complete dataset was performed in 6 batches. To adjust for systematic batch differences, each time a new batch was assayed, 12 PBMC samples from the previous batch were re-extracted and re-assayed. An adjustment factor was derived by comparing the repeat TL values and applied to the new batch.

